

CURRICULUM MANAGEMENT BASED ON LIFE VALUES IN STRENGTHENING STUDENTS' CHARACTER

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Abstract

Character can be strengthened through curriculum management based on life values in every educational institution. The character values promoted in Strengthening Character Education and the Pancasila Student Profile which are inserted in the curriculum and learning process can strengthen students' character who are currently being reduced. The focus of this discussion is to reveal the values of life in Strengthening Character Education and Pancasila Student Profiles, how curriculum management based on life values strengthens the character of students at SDN Cilamaya I and SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District, and the character that can be seen based on the curriculum management based on life values. This research uses a qualitative descriptive approach with data collection techniques are observation, interviews, and documentation studies. Analysis is carried out from the stages of collecting data, classifying, reducing, and conclusions. The results of this research are: *first*, life values are norms that influence a person's actions that are considered important and good that can be applied in schools based on Character Education Strengthening Program and Pancasila Student Profile project. *Second*, curriculum management based on life values is carried out through planning, organizing, implementing, as well as monitoring and evaluating activities carried out by the school principal involving teachers and stakeholders. *Third*, strengthening character at both schools seems to be going well through curriculum management based on life values, with visible character indicators, namely: belief in God Almighty, honest, tolerant, disciplined, creative, independent, cooperation, curiosity, love of the country, care for the environment, and social care.

Keywords: Management, Curriculum, Curriculum Management, Life Values, Character.

INTRODUCTION

The reducing of life values in everyday character is important to be strengthened by the educators. For this reason, it is necessary to make the right decisions by the managers of educational institutions. The option that can be used to strengthen this character is through curriculum management based on life values.

The influence of globalization, such as foreign culture that is not in accordance with the character of the Indonesian nation, needs to be responded wisely. The ease of accessing various information via the internet, which has become increasingly massive during the Covid 19 pandemic among students, has made character problems even more complex. Children's lack of knowledge in filtering western culture causes moral degradation,

including in the age of elementary school. The large number of behavioral deviations by elementary school students, such as fights between students, rape, bullying, drugs, sexual harassment, drinking and smoking in the school environment can affect the existence of young generations in the future (Agung Prihatmojo and Badawi, 2020).

The loss of character education in the learning process during the Covid 19 pandemic has caused character to fade in the family, school, and community. The indicators are many children do not respect their parents, teachers, and other people; loss of sense of courtesy, lack of discipline, loss of sense of caring and helping each other <https://republika.co.id/berita/r6q3g6483/pendidikan-karakter-yang-terasa-hilang-di-masa-pandemi>.

The value-based character of life, especially in Indonesia, is contained in Pancasila as the ideology. There are five main character values of the PPK (Strengthening Character Education) program, namely character values: religious, nationalist, integrity, independence, and collaboration. The impact of this decline in noble character in life that must be overcome, because if early prevention is not carried out immediately, it will influence the mental damage of younger generation, and could even have an impact on the existence of our nation and state in the future.

To make students have noble character or morals, the role of educators is needed, including educators in elementary school. Efforts to strengthen character are very useful in life and have been emphasized in the Strengthening Character Education (PPK) program as outlined in the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education, in Formal Education Units. And currently character is being strengthened in the Pancasila Student Profile project. For the educational process to be effective in forming this character, it is important to implement curriculum management based on life values.

Several studies have shown the conclusion that curriculum management leads to the implementation of planning, actuating, and evaluation functions in character education. It has been implemented well in several places studied and obviously effected to build students' morals or character. Apart from that, curriculum management is believed to be the control of all learning activities which are supported by all educational standards (Slamet Rahayu, 2012; Leny Lukitasari, et al., 2015; Lutfi, Muhammad, 2019; Muhamad Farkhan, 2019; Dewi Syafuroh, 2020; Alfi Zahrotul Hamidah, et al., 2021). Meanwhile, in the research of Durotul Afifah (2016) stated that the characters formed based on curriculum management were the values of divinity (religiosity), honesty, tolerance, discipline, hard work, creativity, independence, democracy, curiosity, national spirit, love homeland, appreciation, communicative, love of peace, likes to read, cares about the environment, social care, and responsibility.

The importance of implementing curriculum management to impact the character of students can be seen from the research results above. Meanwhile the difference in this discussion of curriculum management lies in the values of life at SDN Cilamaya I and

SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District. So, the following discussion focuses on: *first*, life values; *second*, the scope of curriculum management (planning, organizing, implementing, monitoring and evaluating; and *third*, the visible character of curriculum management based on life values.

METHOD

This research uses a qualitative approach, namely research by describing field data in the form of words and language by utilizing various natural methods (Sugiyono, 2018; J.R. Raco 2010 from Creswell, 2008). Based on Moleong (2011), qualitative research is research that intends to understand phenomena about what is experienced by research subjects, for example behavior, perceptions, motivations, actions holistically and by means of descriptions in the form of words and language, especially natural contexts and by utilizing various natural methods.

The aim is to analyze and describe phenomena or research objects through social activities, attitudes, and perceptions of people individually or in groups. Information in the form of words or text collected for analysis. The results of the analysis can be in descriptions or can also be in the form of themes. From this information, researcher makes interpretations to capture the deepest meaning. After that, the researcher make a personal reflection (self-reflection), and explain it with previous research by other scientists. The selection of the place of research is based on purposive sampling, where the school is a favorite or superior school in the area and has a strategic location. Meanwhile, the data collection techniques used in this study were observation, interviews and documentation studies. Data analysis is carried out by collecting data, classifying, reducing, and drawing conclusions.

Curriculum Management

Etymologically, the term curriculum comes from Greek, namely *curir* means runner and *curere* means place to race. So curriculum means the distance that must be covered by runners from the start line to the finish line (Idi, 2014). Based on Casswel and Campbell quoted by Hidayat (2013), the definition of curriculum is a real experience that occurs in the educational process. Curriculum is an educational or teaching plan. Curriculum is also defined as a set of plans and arrangements regarding objectives, content and learning materials as well as methods used as guidelines in carrying out the learning process for students to achieve certain goals (Sukmadinata, 2008; Rusmana, 2009; Ruslan, 2014). And confirmed in Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System (Sisdiknas) defines curriculum as a set of plans and arrangements regarding objectives, content and learning materials as well as the methods used as guidelines for organizing learning activities to achieve certain educational goals.

Ruslan (2014) states that curriculum management is a cooperative, comprehensive, systemic, and systematic management system to realize the achievement of curriculum objectives. Curriculum management is the main substance in schools. The basic principle of curriculum management is to try to ensure that the learning process can run well, by

measuring the achievement of goals by students and encouraging teachers to develop and continuously perfect their learning strategies.

In its implementation, curriculum management must be developed in accordance with the context of school-based management (MBS) and educational unit level curriculum. Operationally, curriculum management and learning systems consist of three functions, namely: planning, implementation, and control.

The function of curriculum management based on life values in forming the character of students is no different from the management function in general. Meanwhile, according to Ruslan (2009), the function of curriculum management can be stated as follow: 1) managing curriculum planning, 2) managing curriculum implementation, 3) carrying out evaluations, 4) managing the formulation of criteria and implementation of grade promotion/graduation, 5) managing material development teaching, learning media, and learning resources, 6) managing extra-curricular and co-curricular development.

Life Values

Life values are norms and life values greatly influence a person's character. Kartono Kartini and Dali Guno (2003) describe values as things that are considered important and good. A kind of person's belief in what should be done, for example honest, sincere; or ideals that someone wants to achieve, for example happiness, freedom.

The life values that can be applied in schools are based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which are rooted in religious values (religious values), moral values, and human (social) values. Religious values are depictions of religious norm. This value is mentioned or explained in the holy books of every religious follower explicitly or implicitly. Examples of religious values are obeying religious commands, respecting all religious believers, respecting each other, and so on.

Moral values reflect someone's moral or behavior. Moral values are like religious values. The difference is that religious values relate to something that has been stated in the holy books. Moral values are not directly mentioned in the scriptures. Moral values relate to moral in general. Examples of moral values are speaking softly to parents, throwing rubbish in the trash, visiting a sick friend, and so on. Social values are values related to the depiction of society. These social values include an attitude of unity (cooperation), honesty and fairness, mutual respect, and maintaining order in the school environment, and so on.

The life values implemented in educational institutions accordance to Strengthening Character Education (PPK) and the Pancasila Student Profile. In the Regulation of the Minister of Education and Culture of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 of 2018 concerning Strengthening Character Education, the recommended characters are: religious, honest, tolerant, disciplined, hardworking, creative, independent, democratic, curious, national spirit, love of the country, appreciate achievements. Meanwhile, there are six elements in the Pancasila Student Profile, namely: having noble character, global diversity, independence, working together, critical reasoning, and creativity. These six

elements are seen as a single unit that supports each other (Panduan Pengembangan Projek Penguatan Profil Pelajar Pancasila, 2022).

Curriculum Management Based on Life Values

First, planning a curriculum based on life values to strengthen the character of students at SDN Cilamaya I and SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District. Activities carried out at the planning stage are a) Outlining the Teaching Program into subject analysis, b) Calculating effective working days and effective teaching hours for each subject, holidays, days for tests, and ineffective days, c) Preparing an annual program, d) Preparing a semester program, e) Learning unit program, and f) Teaching plan. The life values that are inserted in subjects or in the learning process include religious, moral, and social values. Conditions in the field are in accordance with Law no. 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System and Ruslan (2014: 3), that the curriculum contains a set of plans and arrangements as guidelines for implementing learning activities to achieve certain educational goals.

Second, organizing a curriculum based on life values to strengthen the character of students at SDN Cilamaya I and SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District. The organization is decided by the school leadership. The distribution of teaching and other tasks is carried out evenly, according to the teacher's expert and interests. Preparing a predetermined lesson schedule so that teachers teach a maximum of 5 days per week, so that there is one day for teachers to develop scientific through the Subject Teachers' Conference (KKG). School leaders also schedule some activities, namely: remedial, enrichment, extracurricular activities, and refreshments for teachers.

Third, implementing a curriculum based on life values to strengthen the character of students at SDN Cilamaya I and SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District. The implementation of a curriculum based on life values towards strengthening the character of students is carried out through workshops for teachers. This is one of the school supervisor's agendas to maintain the quality of education and schools both at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District. Workshops are held every six months.

Fourth, supervision and evaluation of the life values-based curriculum in strengthening the character of students at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District. Supervision starts from planning curriculum management, organizing, implementing, and evaluating directly by the school principal. Evaluation of teachers is carried out with the aim of determining the achievement of specific learning objectives and identifying student difficulties. And the results of this evaluation are then used by teachers to improve learning activities on an ongoing basis.

In implementing life values-based curriculum management, school principal involves teachers and stakeholders. And the activities are started from planning, implementing, and evaluation. These stages have fulfilled the management function as stated by Ruslan (2009), namely: 1) managing curriculum planning, 2) managing curriculum implementation, 3) carrying out evaluations. Lutfi, Muhammad (2019) who describes the

curriculum management program through planning, implementation, and evaluation in forming student character.

An activity in which the principal, teachers and stakeholders carry out curriculum management activities at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District in forming characters that are useful in the lives of students. The results of this research are what differentiate it from other research (Slamet Rahayu, 2012) which highlights curriculum management from the teacher's side as curriculum implementation, which for teachers should more accurately be called learning management activities.

Strengthening Visible Character through Curriculum Management Based on Life Values

Strengthening character at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District seems to be going well through curriculum management based on life values. Life values are norms or life values that greatly influence students' actions and are important in this situation.

The character formation from elementary age that is visible in these two schools begin with the figure of the teacher as a role model. Based on information and observations in the field, teachers show good model, convey important moral messages in students' lives, give them appreciation, be honest and open mind, and give inspiration and motivation to students. And this is in accordance with teachers' obligations as stated in Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, that in carrying out professional duties, teachers are obliged to: uphold religious and ethical values; maintain and foster national unity.

Because from the examples given by the teacher, those characters are imitated by the students. Students' character can be seen through good model of their teachers. The characters packaged in the curriculum and implemented in the learning process are then seen in students at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District, namely: the character of believing in God Almighty, honest, tolerant, disciplined, creative, independent, cooperative. Cooperation, curiosity, love of the country, caring for the environment, and social care.

This character seems to be proof of the realization of the Strengthening Character Education (PPK) program and the Pancasila Student Profile project. The noble character, global diversity, independence, cooperation, critical reasoning, and creativity are integrated and those are very important in life (Panduan Pengembangan Proyek Penguatan Profil Pelajar Pancasila, 2022).

CONCLUSION

Life values are norms that influence a person's actions; describing values as things that are considered important and good. The values of life applied in the schools are based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia which were incorporated into the Character Education Strengthening Program and the Pancasila

Student Profile project.

Curriculum management based on life values as stated in the Pancasila Student Profile, is carried out in the stages of planning, organizing, implementing, as well as monitoring and evaluating. The curriculum-based life values in strengthening the character of students at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya District Wetan Karawang is implemented by the school principal involving teachers and stakeholders.

The character at SDN Cilamaya I and at SDN Cilamaya IV, Cilamaya Wetan Karawang District seems to be going well through curriculum management based on life values. Implementation of the program to strengthen the character education and profile of Pancasila students, forming characters: believe in Almighty God, honest, tolerant, discipline, creative, independent, cooperation, curious, love the country, care for the environment and social.

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